

DESCRIPTION OF *COLLOTHECA MONASTICA* SP. NOV. (MONOGONONTA: GNESIOTROCHA: COLLOTHECACEAE), A PREDATORY SESSILE ROTIFER FROM THE FOOTHILLS OF THE IBERIAN PYRENEES

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ABSTRACT

A new species of sessile rotifer, *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov., is described. The specimens are usually attached to submerged bryophytes. The new species is ~400 µm long, with the body usually curved towards the substrate. The large funnel shaped infundibulum possesses short non-motile setae on the edge, a dorsal lobe in the form of an intersection sign (∩), a wide V-shaped ventral sinus, and several tufts of erect sensory bristles inside. The foot ends in a short, broad, striated peduncle. The trophi are uncinata with two pairs of long teeth, each with a medial groove in the tooth head. The tube is hyaline with exogenous particles adhered. The resting egg has an oblique ridge at one pole. The adult animal feeds on prey that casually enter the infundibulum. Scanning electron microscopy has revealed two traits not previously described in other species of family Collothecidae: (1) the lining of the infundibulum is studded with cylindrical projections and (2) the integument of the trunk has tubercles. These traits have been reported so far only in the family Atrochidae, so they may be of interest for phylogeny. Other rotifers found at the sampling site are listed, highlighting *Ptygura thalenoensis* Meksuwan, Pholpunthin & Segers, 2011, the first record of this species outside southeastern Asia.

Keywords. Family Collothecidae, order Collotecaceae, predator, *Ptygura thalenoensis*, sessile rotifer, Spain.

RESUMEN

Descripción de *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. (Monogononta: Gnesiotrocha: Collotheceae), un rotífero sésil depredador de las estribaciones del Pirineo ibérico

Se describe una nueva especie de rotífero sésil, *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov., cuyos ejemplares se encuentran generalmente adheridos a briofitos sumergidos. La nueva especie mide unos 400 µm de largo y su cuerpo está generalmente curvado hacia el sustrato. El infundíbulo, de gran tamaño y forma de embudo, posee setas cortas inmóviles en el borde, un lóbulo dorsal en forma de signo de intersección (∩), un seno ventral ancho en forma de V y varios grupos de cerdas sensoriales erectas en su interior. El pie termina en un pedúnculo corto, ancho y estriado. Los trofi son uncinados con dos pares de dientes largos, cada uno con un surco medial en la cabeza del diente. El tubo es hialino con partículas exógenas adheridas. El huevo en reposo tiene una cresta oblicua en un polo. Se alimenta de presas que entran casualmente en el infundíbulo. La microscopía electrónica de barrido ha revelado dos caracteres no descritos previamente en otras especies de la familia Collothecidae: (1) el revestimiento del infundíbulo está tachonado de proyecciones cilíndricas y (2) el tegumento del tronco presenta tubérculos. Estos caracteres han sido descritos hasta ahora sólo en la familia Atrochidae, por lo que pueden ser de interés para la filogenia. Se enumeran otros rotíferos encontrados en el punto de muestreo, destacando *Ptygura thalenoensis* Meksuwan, Pholpunthin & Segers, 2011, el primer registro de esta especie fuera del sudeste asiático.

Palabras clave. Depredador, familia Collothecidae, orden Collotecaceae, *Ptygura thalenoensis*, rotífero sésil, España.

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Introduction

Phylum Rotifera comprises ~2000 small, aquatic metazoans, with three curious features (Wallace & Uyhelji (Smith), 2016). (1) Their ciliated anterior end (corona) is used for movement and/or feeding. In some species the metachronous beating of the cilia creates the illusion of a rotating wheel, but in the adults of the Collothecaceae the corona is replaced by the infundibulum (Hochberg *et al.*, 2019). (2) Rotifers process their food using a set of chitinous jaws composed of up to seven parts that articulate with one another in a complex manner. Thus, these small, jawed animals are members of the Gnathifera clade (Segers, 2004; Wallace *et al.*, 2006; Witek *et al.*, 2009). (3) Rotifera *sensu stricto* possess a syncytial body wall with a dense intracytoplasmic lamina, a characteristic shared with phylum Acanthocephala, thus forming the clade Syndermata or Rotifera *sensu lato*. However, the phylogenetic relationships among Acanthocephala and the various taxa of Rotifera have not been adequately resolved (Funch *et al.*, 2005; Sørensen & Giribet, 2006; Fontaneto & Jondelius, 2011; Wey-Fabrizius *et al.*, 2014; Fontaneto & DeSmet, 2015; Sielaff *et al.*, 2016; Wallace *et al.*, 2019; Hagemann *et al.*, 2023; Vasilikopoulos *et al.*, 2024).

Rotifers are classified in three groups, which differ in their mode of reproduction. Seisonacea (7 spp.) are obligatorily sexual; Bdelloidea (~450 spp.) have been considered exclusively parthenogenetic: compare Birky Jr (2010) and Laine *et al.* (2022); Monogononta (~1600 spp.) are cyclically parthenogenetic (Segers, 2007; Jersabek & Leitner, 2013). Rotifers seem to have undergone rapid adaptive radiation, with Monogononta possessing the greatest morphological diversity (Bininda-Emonds, 2021).

All members of the Seisonacea are epizoic on small marine crustaceans. On the other hand, all species in the subclasses Bdelloidea and Monogononta can move at least for a portion of their life. Yet many of them attach temporarily to a surface to feed. However, about one hundred species of the superorder Gnesiotrocha (Monogononta) are strictly sessile; as adults they live permanently fixed to the substratum being unable to reattach after being dislodged (Edmondson, 1944; Wallace, 1980; Davies *et al.*, 2024).

Specifically, most rotifers of the order Collothecaceae, and of the family Flosculariidae (order Flosculariaceae) are sessile (Hudson & Gosse, 1886; Wallace *et al.*, 2006; Wallace & Snell, 2010; Bielanska-Grajner *et al.*, 2015; Fontaneto & DeSmet, 2015). The offspring in these taxa do not resemble their adult form; after a brief larval stage they metamorphose into the adult form (Wright, 1959). Species of Flosculariidae have a very active corona of motile cilia, malleoramate trophi, and process food by microphagous suspension feeding. The infundibulum in Collothecaceae species functions as a structure for raptorial ambush feeding, capturing prey by closing around them (Meksuwan *et al.*, 2013). These rotifers also possess uncinatate trophi. As a group, Collothecaceae consume protists, rotifers, and other microinvertebrates, connecting them with the microbial loop (Wallace *et al.*, 2015).

Sessile rotifers have been less studied than their planktonic counterparts as they require a more complex processing (Wallace *et al.*, 2006, 2015) including the collection of the macrophytes on which they live; these species also must be identified *in vivo*; in certain cases, identification requires extraction from the sheaths (gelatinous matrices or tubes) they secrete (Meksuwan *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, the current taxonomy presents uncertainties that hinder a comprehensive understanding of the phylogeny of sessile species (Davies *et al.*, 2024; Franch *et al.*, 2024). Nevertheless, these taxa offer interesting research subjects including their evolution, the function of their diverse morphologies, and their ultrastructure, genetics, life history, and habitat-dependent adult reproduction and survival (Lafleur *et al.*, 2024).

Here I describe a new predatory species of sessile rotifer of the genus *Collothecha* Harring, 1913 found in a shallow pond in the foothills of the Iberian Pyrenees. Some of its features characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) could help to better understand the phylogenetic relationships among Collothecidae. We also report other species of sessile rotifers present in this pond, including *Ptygura thalenoensis* Meksuwan, Pholpunthin & Segers, 2011, being the first record of this species outside southeastern Asia.

Material and methods

SAMPLING SITE

A shallow small pond (~50 m diameter) near Monasterio Nuevo de San Juan de la Peña, Jaca, Huesca (Spain) was sampled on June 17, 2024 (Fig. 1). Coordinates: WGS84 42.505978, -0.665202 (Geocentric cartesian: N42°30'21.521", W0°39'54.727"); elevation 1230 m asl) in a mountainous area classified as Cfb (Temperate, no dry season, warm

summer) in the Köppen-Geiger climate classification (Kottek *et al.*, 2006). At the time of sampling, water temperature was 24 °C and salinity 82 ppm. Water and submerged macrophytes were collected, kept in two jars, and transported to the lab at ca. 20 °C. Once in the lab the samples were transferred to glass containers and maintained at a constant temperature of 25 °C until further study, usually within a month. While samples were kept in the laboratory, the water level was maintained by periodically adding mineral water. To examine hydrophytes for sessile rotifers I adapted the protocol of Wallace (1977). Some fragments of macrophytes carrying sessile rotifers were examined under a stereomicroscope to remove predatory free swimming species, and then transferred to plastic Petri dishes (10 cm diameter) with pond water, and kept longer (three months) in a chamber at constant 15 °C with indirect illumination.

Fig. 1. Location of the sampling site in Spain (star) [WGS84 42.505978, -0.665202].

Fig. 1. Localización del punto de muestreo en España (estrella) [WGS84 42.505978, -0.665202].

LIGHT MICROSCOPY (LM)

Animals were examined with an Olympus microscope, model CX43, equipped with an Olympus camera EP50. Observations were photographed or video recorded. Some pictures were stacked with CombineZP software. Images were lightly processed with Microsoft Office software. For preparation of permanent slides the type specimens were isolated, fixed with hot glutaraldehyde 2.5% at 80 °C (Örstan, 2015), mounted with pure glycerol on a slide with a cavity, covered with a circular coverslip, and sealed with DPX. For preparation of the permanent slide of resting eggs, these were isolated, fixed with formaldehyde 4% for 5 minutes, washed in deionized water two times, and then mounted as above.

SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPY (SEM)

For trophi preparation, modified NaOCl (bleach) digestion was used (Segers *et al.*, 1993; De Smet, 1998). In this protocol, tissues were digested in 5% bleach on a circular coverslip for at least 10 minutes; the remaining structures were washed in distilled water (5–7 times) and then air-dried for at least two hours. For resting egg preparation, these were isolated and washed in distilled water two times and then air dried. For whole specimen preparation, an isolated specimen (with or without its sheath) was placed in a drop of deionized water in a depression slide, fixed with a drop of hot (85 °C) 2.6% glutaraldehyde in cacodylate buffer (0.1M) for 15 minutes and then rinsed twice with 0.855 mg/100 mL saccharose cacodylate. After fixation, the specimen was moved to a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube and dehydrated with a graded ethanol series. Lastly, the dehydrated specimen was deposited on a circular coverslip and air-dried for at least two hours.

Circular coverslips with trophi, resting eggs, or dehydrated whole specimens were attached to an Aluminum stub, and sputter coated with platinum. SEM photographs were taken in the electron microscope of the Scientific and Technical Research Area (ACTI) of the University of Murcia (Spain), using FESEM ApreoS.

Results

Submerged macrophytes were identified as the water crowfoot *Ranunculus cf. aquatilis*, *Chara* sp., and a submerged bryophyte of Class Bryopsida. The largest number of sessile specimens were found on the bryophyte leaves. A total of 18 species of rotifers were identified, including seven sessile and 11 free swimming taxa (Table 1). Sessile rotifers belong to genera *Collotheca* (order Collotheceae) and *Ptygura* (order Flosculariaceae). Besides an undescribed species of *Collotheca*, described below, the observation of *Ptygura thalenoensis* stands out as the first record outside the Oriental region and in rather different climatic conditions, since the previous records of this species were in low altitude, subtropical climate conditions (Segers *et al.*, 2010; Meksuwan *et al.*, 2011; Wei *et al.*, 2019).

Table 1. List of rotifer species collected from the pond at Monasterio Nuevo de San Juan de la Peña.

Tabla 1. Lista de especies de rotíferos recolectadas en la charca del Monasterio Nuevo de San Juan de la Peña.

Bdelloidea
<i>Otostephanos donneri</i> Bartoš, 1959
<i>Philodina megalotrocha</i> Ehrenberg, 1832
Ploima
<i>Cephalodella auriculata</i> (Müller, 1773)
<i>Cephalodella</i> sp.
<i>Lecane bulla</i> (Gosse, 1851)
<i>Lecane closterocerca</i> (Schmarda, 1859)
<i>Lecane inermis</i> (Bryce, 1892)
<i>Lecane luna</i> (Müller, 1776)
<i>Lepadella patella</i> (Müller, 1773)
<i>Lepadella triptera</i> (Ehrenberg, 1830)
<i>Mytilina ventralis</i> (Ehrenberg, 1830)
Gnesiotrocha
<i>Collotheca algicola</i> (Hudson, 1886)
<i>Collotheca coronetta</i> (Cubitt, 1869)
<i>Collotheca monastica</i> sp. nov.
<i>Collotheca ornata</i> (Ehrenberg, 1830)
<i>Ptygura beauchampi</i> Edmondson, 1940
<i>Ptygura crystallina</i> (Ehrenberg, 1834)
<i>Ptygura thalenoensis</i> Meksuwan, Pholpunthin & Segers, 2011.

Phylum Rotifera Cuvier, 1817
 Class Eurotatoria De Ridder, 1957
 Subclass Monogononta Plate, 1889
 Superorder Gnesiotrocha Kutikova, 1970
 Order Collotheceae Haring, 1913
 Family Collotheceidae Haring, 1913
 Genus *Collotheca* Haring, 1913

Collotheca monastica sp. nov.

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Figs. 2–13

TYPE SPECIMENS

All type specimens have been deposited in the Museum of Zoology of the University of Navarra (MZNA).

Holotype (MZNA-798605): An adult female attached to a bryophyte leaf mounted on a permanent microscope slide labelled n. 291.

Paratypes. Paratype 1 (MZNA-798606): An adult female mounted on a permanent microscope slide labelled n. 290, with paratype 2. **Paratype 2** (MZNA-798607): A free-swimming larva mounted on a permanent

microscope slide labelled n. 290, with paratype 1. **Paratype 3** (MZNA-798608): A mictic female in its tube with 10 male eggs (embryos) mounted on a permanent microscope slide labelled n. 289. **Paratype 4** (MZNA-798609): Two resting eggs (diapausing embryos) mounted on a permanent microscope slide labelled n. 298.

TYPE LOCALITY

Shallow pond next to Monasterio Nuevo de San Juan de la Peña, Jaca, Huesca (Spain), elevation 1230 m asl (Fig. 2A). Coordinates: GD 42.505978; -0.665202 (GMS N42°30'21.521", W0°39'54.727"). Collected on June 17, 2024. The water level of the pond can vary dramatically between winter and summer (Fig. 2A). Specimens were mostly found on the inner side of leaf insertions of an unidentified submerged bryophyte (Fig. 2B).

Fig. 2. Type locality. A. Pond at Monasterio Nuevo de San Juan de la Peña in August 7, 2024 the driest time at this locality. B. Dark field microphotograph of a specimen of *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. (arrowhead) located at the inner side of a bryophyte leaf insertion. Scale bar: 200 μ m.

Fig. 2. Localidad tipo. A. Charca en el Monasterio Nuevo de San Juan de la Peña el 7 de agosto de 2024, la época más seca en la localidad. B. Microfotografía de campo oscuro de un espécimen de *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. (punta de flecha) localizado en el lado más interno de la inserción de una hoja de briofito. Escala: 200 μ m.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

Collotheca monastica sp. nov. is a sessile rotifer with a wide, five-lobed infundibulum possessing short setae distributed evenly on the edge of the lateral and ventral lobes. Like *Collotheca ferox* (Penard, 1914) and *Collotheca orchidacea* Meksuwan, Pholpunthin & Segers, 2013, the large funnel-shaped infundibulum is held usually angled towards the substrate to which it is attached. However, *C. monastica* sp. nov. is differentiated from *C. ferox* by a smaller dorsal lobe, an abrupt transition (right angle vs. concave) between the dorsal lobe and the lateral lobes, wider ventral lobes, and larger ventral sinus. Compared with *C. orchidacea*, *C. monastica* sp. nov. has a smaller dorsal lobe, abrupt transition between the dorsal and the lateral lobes, less marked lateral and ventral lobes, and shorter uniform setae covering the top edge of the dorsal lobe and the entire edge of the lateral and ventral lobes (Fig. 3).

DESCRIPTION

Habitus. Body usually curved toward the substrate; broad funnel-shaped transparent infundibulum about as long as the trunk, with short non-motile cilia (setae), a dorsal lobe in the form of an intersection-symbol (\cap), and a wide V-shaped ventral sinus; trunk thicker than the base of the infundibulum; dorsal protuberance at the beginning of the foot; foot as long as the trunk; short, broad peduncle. Total length \sim 400 μ m (Fig. 4).

Head (infundibulum). mouth opening seemingly circular (\sim 180 μ m width) (Fig. 5A), with a uniquely protruding dorsal lobe with the shape of the intersection-symbol (\cap), \sim 38 μ m long and \sim 34 μ m wide (Fig. 4B). Lateral lobes somewhat wider than the ventral ones, with a barely marked separation between them (Fig. 3B). The ventral sinus forms a broad, deep angle, and is unciliated (\sim 47 width, \sim 11 μ m depth) (Fig. 3C). The setae (non-motile cilia) are short (\sim 15 μ m length) (Fig. 5B), uniformly distributed all around the infundibulum edge, lacking only in the lateral sides of the dorsal lobe and in the ventral sinus (Fig. 4). Nevertheless, at the ventral

sinus some shorter non-motile cilia can be distinguished in the external side, but they do not overhang the edge. The infundibulum is funnel-shaped (external width ~ 180 , internal width ~ 45 μm , depth from the apex of the dorsal lobe ~ 132 μm) (Fig. 5C). The infundibular lining has several tufts of sensorial bristles (Fig. 5C). The two tiny ventrolateral antennae are located ~ 40 μm from the upper edge of the infundibulum (Fig. 5D). Numerous movable excretophores are located under the integument in rows or in irregular groups over the entire surface, their number increasing with age (Fig. 5E). The lining is covered by minute punctual projections (Fig. 5E). The bottom of the infundibulum is covered by the upper wall of the proventriculus.

Fig. 3. Schemes to compare the infundibular regions of three *Collothecha* species in frontal view: *Collothecha monastica* sp. nov., *Collothecha ferox*, and *Collothecha orchidacea*. Circles mark integumental rings, more prominent (dashed) or less (dotted). Abbreviations: DL = dorsal lobe; LL = lateral lobes; VL = ventral lobes; S = ventral sinus.

Fig. 3. Esquemas para comparar las regiones infundibulares de tres especies de *Collothecha* en vista frontal: *Collothecha monastica* sp. nov., *Collothecha ferox* y *Collothecha orchidacea*. Los círculos indican anillos del integumento, más prominentes (guiones) o menos (puntos). Abreviaturas: DL = lóbulo dorsal; LL = lóbulos laterales; VL = lóbulos ventrales; S = seno ventral.

Fig. 4. Microphotographs of the *habitus* of *Collothecha monastica* sp. nov. *in situ*. A. Whole specimen, optical focus on the central frontal plane. B. Close up of the infundibulum focused on the dorsal lobe. C. Close up of the infundibulum focused on the ventral sinus. Abbreviations: bu = bulge; dl = dorsal lobe; f = foot; i = infundibulum; la = lateral antenna; ll = lateral lobe; p = peduncle; s = setae; t = trunk; vl = ventral lobe; vs = ventral sinus. Scale bars = 100 μm .

Fig. 4. Microfotografías del *habitus* de *Collothecha monastica* sp. nov. *in situ*. A. Especimen completo, foco óptico en el plano frontal central. B. Primer plano del infundíbulo enfocado en el lóbulo dorsal. C. Detalle del infundíbulo enfocado en el seno ventral. Abreviaturas: bu = protuberancia; dl = lóbulo dorsal; f = pie; i = infundíbulo; la = antena lateral; ll = lóbulo lateral; p = pedúnculo; s = setas; t = tronco; vl lóbulo ventral; vs = seno ventral Escalas = 100 μm .

Fig. 5. Microphotographs of the infundibulum of *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. A. Stacked image from four serial microphotographs of the infundibulum in frontal view. B. Close up of the setae (non-motile cilia) bordering the mouth opening. C. Optical frontal section of the infundibulum showing several tufts of sensory bristles (arrowheads). Arrows mark the relative position of the lateral antennae. D. One lateral antenna. E. Close up of the infundibulum with the focus on the lining. Abbreviations: cp = cylindrical projections; dl = dorsal lobe; ex = excretophores; pr = prey; pv = proventriculus; rf = ring folds; s = setae; vl = ventral lobe. Scale bars: A = 100 μ m; B–E = 20 μ m.

Fig. 5. Microfotografías del infundíbulo de *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. A. Imagen apilada a partir de cuatro microfotografías con enfoques en serie del infundíbulo en vista frontal. B. Primer plano de las setas (cilios inmóviles) bordeando la abertura de la boca. C. Sección óptica frontal del infundíbulo que muestra varios mechones de cerdas sensoriales (puntas de flecha). Las flechas marcan la posición relativa de las antenas laterales. D. Una antena lateral. E. Primer plano del infundíbulo enfocado en el forro interior. Abreviaturas: cp = proyecciones cilíndricas; dl = lóbulo dorsal; ex = excretóforos; pr = presa; pv = proventrículo; rf = pliegues en anillo; s = setas; vl = lóbulo ventral. Escalas: A = 100 μ m; B–E = 20 μ m.

Fig. 6. SEM images of the infundibulum of *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. A. whole specimen in dorsal view. Note that the dorsal region of the infundibulum (dotted line) has adhered to the trunk like an inside-out sock (arrow), thus allowing us to study the surface of the infundibulum lining. Arrowheads mark protrusions of the trunk produced by large pennate diatoms stored in the proventriculus. Circle marks a tuft of sensorial bristles. B. The left half of the infundibulum. C. Close up of the ciliate area of a ventral lobe showing the integumental thickening at the base of setae (arrowheads). D. Close up of the external layer of the infundibulum at the boundary between the ventral lobe and the ventral sinus. E. Close up of the surface of the infundibular lining. Note the cylindrical shape of the projections at the edge of the fold (arrowhead). F. Close up of a tuft of sensorial bristles. Abbreviations: bu = bulge; cp = cylindrical projections; dl = dorsal lobe; ei = external integument; f = foot; it = integumental thickening; l = lining of the infundibulum; ll = lateral lobe; p = pores; rf = ring fold; s = setae (non-motile cilia); ss = short setae; t = trunk; vl = ventral lobe; vs = ventral sinus. Scale bars: A = 50 μ m; B = 20 μ m; C–D, F = 5 μ m; E = 2 μ m.

Fig. 6. Imágenes SEM del infundíbulo de *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. A. espécimen entero en vista dorsal. Nótese que la región dorsal del infundíbulo (línea punteada) se ha adherido al tronco como un calcetín dado la vuelta (flecha), lo que nos permite estudiar la superficie del revestimiento del infundíbulo. Las puntas de flecha marcan protuberancias del tronco producidas por grandes diatomeas pennadas almacenadas en el proventrículo. El círculo marca un mechón de cerdas sensoriales. B. La mitad izquierda del infundíbulo. C. Primer plano de la zona ciliada de un lóbulo ventral mostrando el cordón perimetral (puntas de flecha). D. Detalle de la capa externa del infundíbulo en el límite entre un lóbulo ventral y el seno ventral. E. Detalle de la superficie del forro interno del infundíbulo. Obsérvese en el borde del pliegue la forma cilíndrica de las proyecciones (punta de flecha). F. Primer plano de un mechón de cerdas sensoriales. Abreviaturas: bu = protuberancia; cp = proyecciones cilíndricas; dl = lóbulo dorsal; ei = integumento externo; f = pie; it = engrosamiento del integumento; l = forro interno del infundíbulo; ll = lóbulo lateral; p = poros; rf = pliegue en anillo; s = setas (cilios inmóviles); ss = setas cortas; t = tronco; vl = lóbulo ventral; vs = seno ventral. Escalas: A = 50 μ m; B = 20 μ m; C–D, F = 5 μ m; E = 2 μ m.

Fig. 7. Morphological features of the trunk of *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. A. Microphotograph focused on the integument. B. SEM image of the integument surface. C. Microphotograph of the trunk. D. The proventriculus with some prey (diatoms and a gastrotrich). The circle marks the position of the trophi, which is out of focus. E. The stomach, the intestine, and the cloaca. F. Position of the cloaca on the dorsal side. G. Close up of the cloaca. Abbreviations: cl = cloaca; co = cloacal opening; ex = excretophores; f = foot; ie = internal epithelium of the proventriculus; in = infundibulum; it = intestine; od = oviduct; p = pores; pr = prey; pv = proventriculus; re = resting egg (diapausing embryo); se = subitaneous egg; st = stomach; tb = tubercles; ti = trophi; vt = vitellarium. Scale bars: A = 10 μm ; B = 1 μm ; C = 50 μm ; D–F = 20 μm ; G = 5 μm .

Fig. 7. Características morfológicas del tronco de *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. A. Microfotografía enfocada en el integumento. B. Imagen SEM de la superficie del integumento. C. Microfotografía del tronco. D. El proventriculo con alguna presa (diatomeas y un gastrotricho). El círculo marca la posición del trophi, que está fuera de foco. E. El estómago, el intestino y la cloaca. F. Posición de la cloaca en la cara dorsal. G. Primer plano de la cloaca. Abreviaturas: cl = cloaca; co = abertura de la cloaca; ex = excretóforos; f = pie; ie = epitelio interno del proventriculo; in = infundibulum; it = intestino; od = oviducto; p = poros; pr = presa; pv = proventriculo; re = huevo latente (embrión en diapausa); se = huevo subitáneo; st = estómago; tb = tubérculos; ti = trophi; vt = vitellarium. Escalas: A = 10 μm ; B = 1 μm ; C = 50 μm ; D–F = 20 μm ; G = 5 μm .

SEM images show ridges in the external surface of the infundibulum (Fig. 6A–B) and many pores (Fig. 6C–D). At the base of the setae the integument is thicker (Fig. 6C). The internal face of the infundibulum (lining) is studded with cylindrical protrusions (~ 300 nm height, ~ 100 nm width, ~ 1 protrusion per μm^2), each ending in a prismatic structure of ~ 200 nm (Fig. 6E). The lining also has pores (Fig. 6E) and tufts of sensory bristles ~ 10 μm length ~ 150 nm thick grouped in tufts (Fig. 6F).

Trunk. Under LM, the trunk showed a granulate surface (Fig. 7A). SEM revealed that the granulation is composed of tubercles ~ 100 to 250 nm in diameter with a density of ~ 8 tubercles per μm^2 (Fig. 7B). The trunk also has pores, with one pore per ~ 20 tubercles (Fig. 7B). The trunk is spindle-shaped widening after the infundibulum, then progressively decreasing to the cloaca forming a bulge in dorsal position (Fig. 4A). After the infundibulum, inside the trunk the digestive tract continues with the pharyngeal tube, proventriculus, mastax, stomach, and intestine (Fig. 7C). The infundibulum ends in a short, dilatable, dorsoventrally oriented pharyngeal opening (Fig. 5A), which may be anteriorly everted. The pharyngeal opening connects with the proventriculus, a cavity somewhat wider than the bottom of the infundibulum, globose, dilatable and extensible, internally covered by a resistant epithelium (Fig. 7D). In a variable position at the base of the proventriculus is the mastax, which crumbles the prey with the trophi teeth. The densely ciliated stomach has a thick cellular wall and contains mechanically and chemically macerated materials showing a distinct aspect from those of the proventriculus and intestine (Fig. 7C, E). The intestine is globose, with a narrow non-ciliated epithelium,

and usually dark-colored content with granules (Fig. 7C, E). We have never seen the defecation process. The vitellarium is in a ventral position between the proventriculus and the stomach (7C). The oviduct extends under the intestine to reach the cloaca (Fig. 7E). The cloaca is located on the dorsal side of the trunk, just next to the foot, showing a frayed edge after egg deposition (Fig. 7E–G). Due to the dark coloration of the intestine and the copious movable excretophores, it was difficult to distinguish other organs such as digestive glands or the bladder.

Foot. Ventrally curved, length equal to the trunk, with a swelling on the median dorsal side (Fig. 8A). When contracted it does not telescope into the trunk (Fig. 8B). The attachment organ has the form of a truncated conical striated peduncle ($\sim 6 \mu\text{m}$ top width, $\sim 3.5 \mu\text{m}$ height, $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ bottom width) (Fig. 8A and B inset).

Tube. Poorly structured, hyaline with a denser filamentous inner border, and with exogenous particles adhered (Fig. 9A–B). The mucous secretion increases with age and the number of particles suspended in the water (Fig. 9C).

Embryos. Three types of eggs (embryos) were found. *Subitaneous egg*: ovoid ($74.5 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{m}$ length, $44.8 \pm 0.9 \mu\text{m}$ width, $N = 6$), one or two per female (Fig. 10A). The late-stage subitaneous embryos possess a birefringent body (BRB) (Wallace, 1993) and red eyespots with a globule (Fig. 10B). *Male egg*: ovoid shape ($56.5 \pm 1.9 \mu\text{m}$ length, $33.5 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ width, $N = 6$), up to 10 eggs deposited by a mictic female. The late-stage male embryo possesses eyespots with a globule but does not possess a BRB. Morphology of mictic female not different from the amictic one (Fig. 10C). *Resting egg (diapausing embryo)*: ovoid shape ($76.8 \pm 2.0 \mu\text{m}$ length, $53.8 \pm 0.0 \mu\text{m}$ width; $N = 3$) with an orange colored embryo, covered by an outer thin transparent shell ($90.0 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{m}$ length, $N = 2$) (Fig. 10D) which can be lost (Fig. 10E), and an internal rigid shell with an oblique incomplete apical ridge (Fig. 10D–F). SEM images revealed many bacteria and small diatoms adhered to its surface (Fig. 10G); the ridge runs only half the perimeter, leaving the opposite surface without ornamentation (Fig. 10H); the ridge is double with a medial groove (Fig. 10I).

Fig. 8. Foot of *Collothecha monastica* sp. nov. A. Microphotograph of the extended foot of a specimen. B. Aspect of the contracted foot of another specimen with its infundibulum partially contracted. Note the apparent ventral position of the peduncle. Inset: Enlargement of the respective attachment organ. Abbreviations: ao = attachment organ; bu = bulge; ds = dorsal swelling; fm = foot muscle; i = infundibulum; it = intestine; pv = proventriculus; st = stomach; vi = vitellarium. Scale bars: A–B = 50 μm ; inset = 5 μm .

Fig. 8. Pie de *Collothecha monastica* sp. nov. A: Microfotografía del pie extendido de un espécimen. B: Aspecto del pie contraído de otro espécimen con su corona parcialmente desplegada. Nótese la posición aparentemente ventral del pedúnculo. Recuadros: Ampliaciones del órgano de inserción de cada imagen. Abreviaturas: ao = órgano de anclaje; bu = protuberancia; ds = engrosamiento dorsal; fm = músculo del pie; i = infundibulum; it = intestino; pv = proventriculo; st = estómago; vi = vitellarium. Escalas: A–B = 50 μm ; recuadros = 5 μm .

Fig. 9. The tube of *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. *in situ*. A. Microphotograph of a female in her tube with two diapausing embryos (resting eggs). B. An adult female in her tube with a resting egg. Note the fibrous appearance of the inner side (black arrowheads) and its connections with the eggshell (white arrowhead). C. Ventrolateral view of an adult female in her thickened hyaline tube with many exogenous particles adhered. Abbreviations: ep = exogenous particles; re = resting egg; t = tube; tl = tube lumen.

Fig. 9. El tubo de *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. *in situ*. A. Microfotografía de una hembra en su tubo con dos embriones en diapausa (huevos latentes). B. Una hembra adulta en su tubo con un huevo latente. Nótese el aspecto fibroso de la cara interna del tubo (puntas de flecha negras) y sus conexiones con la cáscara del huevo (punta de flecha blanca). C. Vista ventrolateral de una hembra adulta en su tubo hialino engrosado con muchas partículas exógenas adheridas. Abreviaturas: ep = partículas exógenas; re = huevo latente; t = tubo; tl = lumen del tubo.

Fig. 10. Embryos of *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. by light microscopy (A to F) and scanning electron microscopy (G to I). A. Early stage of a subitaneous diploid parthenogenetic embryo. B. Late stage of a subitaneous embryo. C. Male haploid embryos. D. Two diapausing embryos (resting eggs) with the outer shell intact. E. Diapausing embryo with the outer shell detached. F. Diapausing embryos without the outer thin shell. Note the oblique ridge in one pole. G. SEM image of a resting egg with many bacteria and diatoms adhered. Arrowhead marks the oblique ridge. H. View of the opposite side of the ridge on another resting egg. Arrowhead marks the starting of the ridge. Close-up of the oblique ridge of another resting egg. Arrowheads mark the medial groove at the ridge summit. Abbreviations: br = birefringent body (BRB); em = embryo; ey = eyespot; es = early-stage embryo; is = inner shell; ls = late-stage embryo; mf = foot of the mictic female; or = oblique ridge; os = outer shell. Scale bars: A–F = 50 μ m; G–H = 20 μ m; I = 10 μ m.

Fig. 10. Embriones de *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. por microscopía óptica (A a F) y microscopía electrónica de barrido (G a I). A. Etapa temprana de un embrión partenogenético diploide subitáneo. B. Etapa tardía de un embrión subitáneo. C. Embriones haploides masculinos. D. Dos embriones en diapausa (huevos latentes) con la cáscara exterior intacta. E. Huevo latente con la cáscara externa desprendida. F. Huevos latentes sin la cáscara delgada externa. Nótese la cresta oblicua en un polo. G. Imagen SEM de un huevo latente con muchas bacterias y diatomeas adheridas. La punta de flecha marca la cresta oblicua. H. Vista de otro huevo latente por el lado opuesto a la cresta. La punta de flecha marca el comienzo de la cresta. Primer plano de la cresta oblicua de otro huevo latente. Las puntas de flecha marcan el surco medial en la cima de la cresta. Abreviaturas: br = cuerpo birrefringente (BRB); em = embrión; ey = mancha ocular; es = embrión en estadio temprano; is = cáscara interior; ls = embrión en estadio tardío; mf = pie de la hembra mítica; or = cresta oblicua; os = cáscara exterior. Escalas: A–F = 50 μ m; G–H = 20 μ m; I = 10 μ m.

Fig. 11. *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. free-swimming larvae. A. Newly hatched larva. Note the remnant of an eggshell. B. Entire larva. C. Close up of anterior end. D. Close up of trunk region. E. Close up of caudal end. Abbreviations: ao = attachment organ; br = birefringent body (BRB); cc = ciliate corona; co = cloaca opening; es = eggshell; ey = eyespot; i = infundibulum; pg = pedal glands; pv = proventriculus; s = setae; si = stomach and intestine; tc = terminal tuft of cilia; te = thickened epithelium; ti = trophi. Scale bars: A–B = 50 μ m; C–E = 20 μ m.

Fig. 11. Larvas de vida libre de *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. A. Larva recién eclosionada. Nótese la cáscara de huevo remanente. B. Larva entera. C. Primer plano del extremo anterior. D. Primer plano de la región del tronco. E. Primer plano del extremo caudal. Abreviaturas: ao = órgano de anclaje; br = cuerpo birrefringente (BRB); cc = corona ciliada; co = apertura de la cloaca; es = cáscara de huevo; ey = mancha ocular; i = infundibulo; pg = glándulas pedales; pv = proventriculus; s = setas; si = estómago e intestino; tc = penacho terminal de cilios; te = epitelio engrosado; ti = trophi. Escalas: A–B = 50 μ m; C–E = 20 μ m.

Fig. 12. SEM images of *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. trophi. A. Whole view of the trophi of a specimen. B. Close up of the head tooth of another specimen. Inset: When soft tissues are digested with bleach, the trophi of some rotifer prey stored in the proventriculus may be also revealed, in this case the trophi of *Lepadella* sp. C. Schematic drawing of the trophi. Abbreviations: f = fulcrum; m = manubrium; mg = medial groove; r = rami; sp = scleropilli; th = tooth head; ts = tooth shaft. Scale bars: A and inset = 5 μ m; B = 2 μ m.

Fig. 12. Imágenes SEM de trophi de *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. A: Vista completa de trophi de un espécimen. B: Primer plano del diente de la cabeza de otro espécimen. Recuadro: Cuando los tejidos blandos se digieren con lejía, también pueden aparecer los trophi de algún rotífero presa almacenada en el proventriculo, en este caso el de *Lepadella* sp. C: dibujo esquemático de trophi. f fulcrum, m manubrium, mg surco medial, r rami, sp scleropilli, th cabeza de diente, ts eje del diente. Escalas: A y recuadro = 5 μ m; B = 2 μ m.

Free swimming larva. Since several *Collotheca* species were collected at the sampling site, only newly hatched larvae from subitaneous eggs confined in the tube of adult females were studied to ensure their belonging to *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. Larvae are $\sim 200 \mu\text{m}$ long \times $\sim 40 \mu\text{m}$ wide (Fig. 11A–B). The anterior end possesses active cilia and two red eyespots, each with a prominent globule (Fig. 11A–C). The mouth opens to the infundibulum ($\sim 40 \mu\text{m}$ length, $\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$ width), which has setae $\sim 6 \mu\text{m}$ long at its upper edge, directed inwards (Fig. 11C). These are less active than the cilia of the corona. A thickened epithelium connects the infundibulum with the proventriculus (Fig. 11B–D). The trophus is located at the base of the proventriculus; the morphology is as in the adult (Fig. 11D). The intestine shows a granulated BRB (Fig. 11E). At the beginning of the foot, the cloacal orifice is in a dorsal position (Fig. 11E). The foot width does not initially differ from the trunk, but progressively decreases to its end, showing two elongated pedal glands (Fig. 11B, E). The attachment organ is formed by a discoidal cavity covered by the terminal fold of the foot and a tuft of very active cilia that begins at the upper edge of the disc and protrudes from the terminal fold (Fig. 11E).

Trophi. Uncinate. Poorly defined separation between manubria and rami. Rami with well-developed scleropilli. Upright fulcrum (Fig. 12A). Two pairs of uncinal teeth with a thin, long, curved shaft, and thicker head with medial groove (Fig. 12B), ending in a sharp point.

FEEDING BEHAVIOR

Collotheca monastica sp. nov. usually lies in wait completely motionless: the body is curved towards the substrate, the infundibulum is expanded with the sinus close to the surface of the macrophyte, and the lobes (dorsal, lateral and ventral) extended. The lobes may be in contact with the substrate. Prey size and type are variable and range from a few μm in size (species of Choanozoa) to more than $100 \mu\text{m}$ (various protists, diatoms, gastrotrichs, or planktonic rotifers). The sequence of prey capture is shown in Fig. 13 and in the Supplementary material. When a mobile prey casually enters the infundibular space, it is detected by the internal sensory bristles, and the lobes fold inwards to close the entering; first the cilia enclose the prey (Fig. 13 lower right corner) and then the lobes follow. The internal lining of the infundibulum contracts, separating itself from the external integument thus narrowing the infundibular cavity. After a few seconds, the external integument suddenly and strongly contracts while the proventriculus rises and the pharyngeal tube widens, so that trapped prey are transferred to the proventriculus. Immediately the proventriculus closes and the infundibulum recovers its ambush position. Prey are stored for some time densely packed in the proventriculus while the trophi macerate them from the underside of the proventriculus, introducing the fragments into the stomach. The stomach digests the food. We have never seen the process of defecation, nor the regurgitation of prey stored in the proventriculus if that ever occurs.

Fig. 13. Feeding behavior of *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. Five frames from a video sequence of the capture of a gastrotrich. The time elapsed from the entry of the prey into the infundibulum are indicated in the upper left corner of each frame. Note how the lining of the infundibulum separates from the integument showing a transitory pseudocoelomic space between the two layers (arrowhead). The dotted line marks the pharyngeal tube opening. The last image (lower right corner) does not correspond to the same sequence but to a frontal view of another specimen with the lobes partially closed. Abbreviations: dl = dorsal lobe; i = infundibulum; ie = internal epithelium of the proventriculus; ll = lateral lobes; pht = pharyngeal tube; pr = prey; pv = proventriculus; vl = ventral lobes. Scale bar = $50 \mu\text{m}$ for all images (same scale).

Fig. 13. Comportamiento de alimentación de *Collotheca monastica* sp. nov. Cinco fotogramas de una secuencia de vídeo de la captura de un gastrotrico. Los tiempos transcurridos desde la entrada de la presa en el infundíbulo se indican en la esquina superior izquierda de cada fotograma. Obsérvese cómo el forro del infundíbulo se separa del integumento, mostrando un espacio pseudocelómico transitorio entre las dos capas (punta de flecha). La línea punteada marca la abertura del tubo faríngeo. La última imagen (esquina inferior derecha) no corresponde a la misma secuencia, sino a una vista frontal de otro ejemplar con los lóbulos parcialmente cerrados. Abreviaturas: dl = lóbulo dorsal; i = infundíbulo; ie = epitelio interno del proventrículo; ll = lóbulos laterales; pht = tubo faríngeo; pr = presa; pv = proventrículo; vl = lóbulos ventrales. Escala: $50 \mu\text{m}$ para todas las imágenes (misma escala).

ETYMOLOGY

The species name *monastica* refers to the place where it was found, a pond next to a monastery.

DISTRIBUTION

The species is known from its type locality only.

Discussion

Compared with most Collothecidae (Montgomery, 1903; Koste, 1978; Meksuwan *et al.*, 2013; Walsh *et al.*, 2017; Davies *et al.*, 2024), *Collothea monastica* sp. nov. has some distinctive features: (1) the habit (curved *vs.* upright), (2) the morphology of the infundibulum (funnel-shaped *vs.* bowl-shaped), (3) the absence of diaphragm separating two regions in the infundibulum, (4) the absence of motile cilia both at the edge and inside the infundibulum, (5) the resting-egg ornamentation (smooth with an oblique ridge *vs.* spurs or spines), (6) a longitudinal groove at the head of the uncinial teeth, (7) the type of diet (macrophagous *vs.* microphagous), and (8) the morphology of the peduncle (thick and short *vs.* narrow and elongated).

Specifically, the non-motility of the setae of the infundibular edge and the absence of motile cilia in the infundibular lining of *Collothea monastica* sp. nov. could be of phylogenetic interest. On the one hand, most rotifers of the family Collothecidae (*Collothea* and *Stephanoceros*) possess long setae that can make undulating movements and some motile cilia at the edge of the infundibulum or in the diaphragm that direct prey (mostly protists) into the digestive tract (Montgomery, 1903). On the other hand, species of the family Atrochidae do not have cilia of any kind at the infundibulum. Thus, the loss of setae motility could be an adaptive shift from a microphagous to a macrophagous diet.

The involvement of long setae or cilia in the active capture of small prey by most Collothecidae suggests that they can detect prey externally, although it is not known whether the prey-sensing structures are the motile setae or others (Montgomery, 1903). However, species in family Atrochidae, like *Cupelopagis vorax* (Leidy, 1857), lacking any type of infundibular cilia or setae, are able to orient themselves towards the prey to capture it, which also means that they are able to detect them at a distance, probably by detection of water vibrations by the sensory bristles of the lateral antennae or the infundibular tufts (Bevington *et al.*, 1995). On the contrary, in *C. monastica* sp. nov. the setae of its infundibular rim do not move at all, and they do not change orientation to capture prey. This therefore suggests that in *C. monastica* sp. nov. neither the setae on the edge of the infundibulum, nor the lateral antennae, nor the internal tufts of sensory bristles are capable of detecting water vibrations produced by the prey. Its infundibulum only closes when prey physically contact the bristles of the internal sensory tufts. The short, rigid setae of its infundibular edge would not be mechanoreceptors but simply facilitate retention of the prey before the lobes close completely. Our observations seem to indicate that in *C. monastica* the entry of the prey is passive and casual.

Our SEM images show two traits of *C. monastica* sp. nov. not previously reported for any species in the family Collothecidae, except for *Cupelopagis vorax*: (1) tubercles on the integument of the trunk (Stokes, 1896; Gast, 1899-1990; Hochberg *et al.*, 2017), and (2) the scattered cylindrical projections on the inner side of the infundibulum. The latter trait has not been specifically reported; however, by means of LM, the lining of the infundibulum of *Cupelopagis* Forbes, 1882 has been described as having a “hispid appearance” (Stokes, 1896) or with “minute conical projections” (Montgomery, 1903), which could correspond to the structures shown by our LM and SEM images from the infundibular lining of *C. monastica* sp. nov. Considering the usual diet of both *C. monastica* sp. nov. and *Cupelopagis*, both of which feed on large prey with rigid external structures (e.g., loricated planktonic rotifers), the function of these cylindrical projections may have two functions: 1) to keep prey in place, analogous to the filiform papillae of the vertebrate tongue (Kleinteich & Gorb, 2016), and/or 2) to protect the infundibular lining, minimizing direct friction.

There are few ultrastructural works on species of Collotheceae (e.g., Hochberg & Hochberg, 2017; Hochberg *et al.*, 2017, 2019; Yang *et al.*, 2019), therefore we cannot affirm whether the features found in *C. monastica* sp. nov., i.e. tubercles of the integument and cylindrical projections of the infundibular lining, are exclusive or could also be found in other species. Since *Collothea* and *Cupelopagis* belong to different families of Collotheceae, an ultrastructural comparative TEM study of the trunk integument and of the infundibular lining of these and other Collothecidae species could shed light on their adaptive significance, and on the potential phylogenetic value of these traits.

In summary, the anatomical and behavioral similarities between *Collothea monastica* sp. nov. and *Cupelopagis vorax* suggest a phylogenetic proximity between Atrochidae and the group of species formed by *Collothea ferox*, *C. monastica* sp. nov., and *C. orchidacea*, as already pointed out by Meksuwan *et al.* (2013) based on their macrophagous diet. We have shown that some of these similarities can be traced at the ultrastructural level and deserve further scrutiny with TEM or other histological techniques. Ultrastructural studies could also improve

our understanding of the biology and development of Collothecidae. For example, when the internal layer of the infundibulum contracts, it separates from the external layer, showing a wide pseudocoelomic space; the external layer seems to be formed by a syncytial integument with ICL, while the internal layer could be an internal organ lacking ICL. This could be confirmed with TEM.

Our description of *C. monastica* sp. nov. calls for ultrastructural studies to better understand the biology of these fascinating animals, and help characterize traits used in phylogenetic analyses to unravel the evolutionary relationships of sessile rotifers.

Supplementary material

Video recording of the feeding behavior of *Collothecha monastica* sp. nov. Long video (2 min 42 s); Short video (30 s).

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors of this article declare that they have no financial, professional or personal conflicts of interest that could have inappropriately influenced this work.

References

- Bevington, D.J., White, C. & Wallace, R.L., 1995. Predatory behavior of *Cupelopagis vorax* (Rotifera; Collothecacea; Atrochidae) on protozoan prey. In: Ejsmont-Karabin, J. & Pontin, R.M. (eds) Rotifera VII. *Developments in Hydrobiology*, vol 109. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-009-1583-1_29
- Bielanska-Grajner, I., Ejsmont-Karabin, J. & Radwan, S., 2015. Rotifers (Rotifera monogononta). *Freshwater Fauna of Poland*, 32. Lodz University Press.
- Bininda-Emonds, O., 2021. 18S rRNA variability maps reveal three highly divergent, conserved motifs within Rotifera. *BMC Ecology and Evolution*, 21: 118. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12862-021-01845-2>
- Birky Jr, C., 2010. Positively negative evidence for asexuality. *Journal of Heredity*, 101 (Supplement I)_ S42-S45. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jhered/esq014>
- Davies, N., Lafleur, A., Hochberg, R., Walsh, E.J. & Wallace, R.L., 2024. Key to sessile gnesiotrochan rotifers: Families, monospecific species in Flosculariidae, species of Atrochidae, Conochilidae, and *Limnias*. *Zootaxa*, 5397 (4): 497–520. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5397.4.3>
- De Smet, W., 1998. Preparation of rotifer trophi for light and scanning electron microscopy. *Hydrobiologia*, 387/388: 117-121. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1017053518665>
- Edmondson, W., 1944. Ecological studies of sessile Rotatoria: Part I. Factors affecting distribution. *Ecological Monographs*, 14 (1): 31-66. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1961631>
- Fontaneto, D. & De Smet, W.H., 2015. Chapter 4: Rotifera. In: Andreas Schmidt-Rhaesa (eds.). *Handbook of Zoology, Gastrotricha, Cycloneuralia and Gnathifera. Volume 3, Gastrotricha and Gnathifera*. München, Boston: De Gruyter. 217-286. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110274271.217>
- Fontaneto, D. & Jondelius, U., 2011. Broad taxonomic sampling of mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I does not solve the relationships between Rotifera and Acanthocephala. *Zoologischer Anzeiger*, 250: 80–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcz.2010.11.005>
- Franch, V., Meksuwan, P. & Wallace, R., 2024. The dorsal plate is a critical feature in the reassessment of the rotiferan genus *Ptygura* (Monogononta; Gnesiotrocha; Flosculariidae). *Zootaxa*, 5428 (1): 107–123. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5428.1.5>

- Funch, P., Sørensen, M. & Obst, M., 2005. On the phylogenetic position of Rotifera – have we come any further? *Hydrobiologia*, 546: 11-28. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-005-4093-6>
- Gast, R., 1899-1990. Beiträge zur Kenntnis von *Apsilus vorax* (Leidy). *Zeitschrift für wissenschaftliche Zoologie*, 67: 167-214. Available from <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/43263961> [accessed 19 Sep. 2024].
- Hagemann, L., Mauer, K.M., Hankeln, T., Schmidt, H. & Herlyn, H., 2023. Nuclear genome annotation of wheel animals and thorny headed worms: inferences about the last common ancestor of Syndermata (Rotifera s.l.). *Hydrobiologia*, 851: 2827-2844. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-023-05268-6>
- Hochberg, A. & Hochberg, R., 2017. Musculature of the sessile rotifer *Stephanoceros fimbriatus* (Rotifera: Gnesiotrocha: Collotheceae) with details on larval metamorphosis and development of the infundibulum. *Zoologischer Anzeiger*, 268: 84-95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcz.2016.09.002>
- Hochberg, R., Walsh, E. & Wallace, R., 2017. The ultrastructure of the integument and proventriculus in the raptorial rotifer *Cupelopagis vorax* (Monogononta: Collotheceae: Atrochidae). *Invertebrate Biology*, 136 (1): 50-61. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ivb.12161>
- Hochberg, R., Yang, H., Hochberg, A., Walsh, E., & Wallace, R., 2019. When heads are not homologous: the coronae of larval and adult collotheceid rotifers (Rotifera: Monogononta: Collotheceae). *Hydrobiologia*, 844: 191–207. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-018-3760-3>
- Hudson, C.T. & Gosse, P.H., 1886. *The Rotifera, or Wheel Animalcules, Vol. 1*. Longmans, Green & Co. London. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.39555>
- Jersabek, C. & Leitner, M., 2013. The Rotifer World Catalog. Available from <http://www.rotifera.hausdernatur.at> [accessed 19 Sep. 2024].
- Kleinteich, T. & Gorb, S., 2016. Frog tongue surface microstructures: functional and evolutionary patterns. *Beilstein Journal of Nanotechnology*, 7: 893–903. <https://doi.org/10.3762/bjnano.7.81>
- Koste, W., 1978. *Rotatoria. Die Rädertiere Mitteleuropas*. Gebrüder Borntraeger, Stuttgart.
- Kottek, M., Grieser, J., Beck, C., Rudolf, B. & Rubel, F., 2006. World Map of the Köppen-Geiger climate classification updated. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, 15 (3): 259-263. <https://doi.org/10.1127/0941-2948/2006/0130>
- Lafleur, A., Davies, N., Hochberg, R., Walsh, E. & Wallace, R., 2024. Key to sessile gnesiotrochan rotifers: *Floscularia* (Monogononta; Flosculariidae). *Zootaxa*, 5471 (4): 401-421. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5471.4.1>
- Laine, V., Sackton, T. & Meselson, M., 2022. Genomic signature of sexual reproduction in the bdelloid rotifer *Macrotrachella quadricornifera*. *Genetics*, 220 (2): iyab221. <https://doi.org/10.1093/genetics/iyab221>
- Meksuwan, P., Pholpunthin, P. & Segers, H., 2011. Diversity of sessile rotifers (Gnesiotrocha, Monogononta, Rotifera) in Thale Noi Lake, Thailand. *Zootaxa* 2997: 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.2997.1.1>
- Meksuwan, P., Pholpunthin, P. & Segers, H., 2013. The Collotheceidae (Rotifera, Collotheceae) of Thailand, with the description of a new species and an illustrated key to the Southeast Asian fauna. *ZooKeys*, 315: 1-16. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.315.5330>
- Montgomery, T., 1903. On the morphology of the rotatorian Family Flosculariidae. *Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia*, 55: 363-395. Available from <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/6600605> [accessed 19 Sep. 2024].
- Örstan, A., 2015. A method for the preservation of bdelloid rotifers for taxonomical and anatomical studies. *Quekett Journal of Microscopy*, 42: 355-359.
- Segers, H., 2004. Rotifera: Monogononta. In: Yule, C.M. & H.S. Yong (eds.). *Freshwater Invertebrates of the Malaysian Region*. K.L. Academy of Sciences of Malaysia: 106-120.
- Segers, H., 2007. Annotated checklist of the rotifers (Phylum Rotifera), with notes on nomenclature, taxonomy and distribution. *Zootaxa*, 1564: 1-104. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.1564.1.1>
- Segers, H., Meksuwan, P. & Sanoamuang, L., 2010. New records of sessile rotifers (Phylum Rotifera: Flosculariacea, Collotheceae) from Southeast Asia. *Belgian Journal of Zoology*, 140 (2): 235-240. <http://doi.org/10.26496/bjz.2010.174>

- Segers, H., Murugan, G., & Dumont, H., 1993. On the taxonomy of the Brachionidae: description of *Plationus* n. gen. (Rotifera, Monogononta). *Hydrobiologia*, 268: 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00005736>
- Sielaff, M., Schmidt, H., Struck, T., Rosenkranz, D., Welch, D., Hankeln, T. & Herlyn, H., 2016. Phylogeny of Syndermata (syn. Rotifera): Mitochondrial gene order verifies epizoic Seisonidea as sister to endoparasitic Acanthocephala within monophyletic Hemirotifera. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 96: 79-92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2015.11.017>
- Sørensen, M.V. & Giribet, G., 2006. A modern approach to rotiferan phylogeny: combining morphological and molecular data. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 40: 585–608. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2006.04.001>
- Stokes, A., 1896. Notes on the genus *Apsilus* and other American Rotifera. *Journal of the Royal Microscopical Society*, 1896: 260-278. Available from <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/49597672> [accessed 19 Sep. 2024].
- Vasilikopoulos, A., Herlyn, H., Fontaneto, D. *et al.*, 2024. Whole-genome analyses converge to support the Hemirotifera hypothesis within Syndermata (Gnathifera). *Hydrobiologia* 851: 2795–2826. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-023-05451-9>
- Wallace, R., 1977. Distribution of sessile rotifers in an acid bog pond. *Archiv für Hydrobiologie* 79 (4): 478–505.
- Wallace, R., 1980. Ecology of sessile rotifers. In: Dumont, H.G., Rotatoria. *Developments in Hydrobiology (Vol. 1)*. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-009-9209-2_31
- Wallace, R. 1993. Phylogeny of the phylum Rotifera: a workshop. *Hydrobiologia*, 255-256: 491-493. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00025878>
- Wallace, R. & Snell, T., 2010. Rotifera. In: Thorp, J.H. & Covich, A.P. (eds.). *Ecology and Classification of North American Freshwater Invertebrates*. Elsevier Inc., Amsterdam: 173–235.
- Wallace, R. & Uyhelji (Smith), H., 2016. Rotifera. *Reference Module in Earth Systems and Environmental Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-409548-9.09551-8>
- Wallace, R., Snell, T., Ricci, C. & Nogrady, T., 2006. *Rotifera. Biology, Ecology and Systematics* 2nd ed., Vol. 1. Backhuys Publishers. Leiden.
- Wallace, R., Snell, T. & Smith, H., 2015. Phylum Rotifera. In: *Thorp and Covich's Freshwater Invertebrates*. Elsevier Inc.: 225-271. <http://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-385026-3.00013-9>
- Wallace, R., Snell, T., Walsh, E., Sarma, S. & Segers, H., 2019. Phylum Rotifera. In: *Thorp and Covich's Freshwater Invertebrates*, 4th Edition. Elsevier Inc.: 219-267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-385024-9.00008-3>
- Walsh, E., May, L. & Wallace, R., 2017. A metadata approach to documenting sex in phylum Rotifera: diapausing embryos, males, and hatchlings from sediments. *Hydrobiologia*, 796: 265-276 (Supplemental Document). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-016-2712-z>
- Wei, N., Jersabek, C. & Yang, Y., 2019. Rotifers from China (Western Guangdong Province), with description of *Lecane zhanjiangensis* sp. nov. (Rotifera: Monogononta: Lecanidae). *Zootaxa*, 4603 (1): 66-80. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4603.1.3>
- Wey-Fabrizius, A., Herlyn, H., Rieger, B., Rosenkranz, D., Wite, A., Welch, D., . . . & Hankeln, T., 2014. Transcriptome Data Reveal Syndermatan Relationships and Suggest the Evolution of Endoparasitism in Acanthocephala via an Epizoic Stage. *PLoS ONE*, 9 (2): . <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0088618>
- Witek, A., Herlyn, H., Ebersberger, I., Welch, D. & Hankeln, T., 2009. Support for the monophyletic origin of Gnathifera from phylogenomics. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 53: 1037–1041 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2009.07.031>
- Wright, S., 1959. Development of the peduncle in a sessile rotifer. *The Journal of the Quekett Microscopical Club, Series 4*, 5 /4(): 231-234.
- Yang, H., Hochberg, R., Walsh, E.J. & Wallace, R.L., 2019. Systematic distribution of birefringent bodies in Rotifera and first evidence of their ultrastructure in *Acyclus inquietus* (Gnesiotrocha: Collothecaceae). *Hydrobiologia*, 844: 209–219. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-018-3784-8>